

Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and
Sustainable Economic Development

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

The BRACE Review Checklist

Prepared for Registration to Zenodo

Submitted 08/07/2025

Centre(s):

ENEA Centro Ricerche Bologna,

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Section 1: General Information

1. Review Title	Enabling informed decisions for Climate Risk Management. The BRACE protocol.
2. Named contact	Melania Michetti
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4. Organizational affiliations of the review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENEA • University of Bologna
5. Funding sources	This study was carried out within the RETURN Extended Partnership and received funding from the European Union Next-Generation EU (National Recovery and Resilience Plan – NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3 – D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005).
6. Conflicts of interest	The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.
7. Type of review	Review Type: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scoping review <input type="checkbox"/> Rapid review <input type="checkbox"/> Systematic review <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
8. Languages	English, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian
9. Countries	Worldwide
10. Keywords	Climate risk reduction; Climate crisis management; Hazards; Adaptation barriers; Adaptation enablers.

Section 2: Review stage and timeline

Review timescale		
11. Start date	May 2023	
12. Completion date	December 2024	
Stage of review at time of this submission:		
13. Review stage <i>(Please check all that apply)</i>	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Piloting of the study selection process	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Data extraction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Data analysis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section 3: Review Methods

14. Objectives or review question(s)	What are the main barriers and enablers that shape policymaking for effective climate risk mitigation and crisis management?
15. Literature Search	Comprehensive literature searches of electronic bibliographic database Scopus; selecting articles published in journals indexed in the Scopus database.
16. Search strategy	<p>The search strategy was designed to identify peer-reviewed journal articles relevant to the review question by using targeted search queries in Scopus.</p> <p>Separate search strings were developed for two main thematic areas: climate risk reduction and crisis management. Each query combined relevant keywords and phrases using Boolean operators (AND, OR), focusing on concepts such as climate risk, risk reduction, policy, barriers, enablers, crisis management, and decision-making.</p> <p>Search terms were tailored to the Scopus database using free-text terms only. Filters were applied to include only peer-reviewed articles published in English. The final set of queries and search results will be documented and included as an appendix to the review.</p>
17. Protocol and registration	Documented but not registered protocol
18. Eligibility criteria	<p><u>Years of publication:</u> 2000-2022 (included).</p> <p><u>Languages:</u> English, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian, French.</p> <p><u>Type of Source:</u> Journal</p> <p><u>Type of Document:</u> Article</p> <p><u>Subject Areas:</u> Social Sciences; Multidisciplinary; Decision Sciences; Business, Management and Accounting; Economics, Econometrics and Finance; Psychology.</p> <p><u>Subject SubAreas, "Physical Sciences":</u> General Environmental Science; Environmental Science</p>

	(miscellaneous); Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law.
19. Selection of sources of evidence	Limited to only peer reviewed articles (no grey, no reports, no policy documents, no expert opinions)
20. Data charting process	Data from the included articles were extracted by one member of the review team and subsequently checked for accuracy and completeness by a second team member. Any discrepancies identified during the checking process were resolved through discussion between the two members.
21. Data items	<p>Data items extracted from each included article are reported in the appendix of the review analysis. An overview is the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General descriptive dimensions (Bibliographic information, country or region of study, study aim(s) and objectives, type of study or methodological approach, research design, stage of policy process, etc.) • Analytical dimensions (barriers and enablers) • Relevant contextual variables • Recommendations or implications for policymaking • Any assumptions or limitations noted by the authors
22. Data extraction	1) Authors, 2) Author full names, 3) Author(s) Identification Code, 4) Title, 5) Year, 6) Source title, 7) Volume, 8) Issue, 9) Art. No., 10) Page start, 11) Page end, 12) Page count, 13) Cited by, 14) DOI, 15) Link, 16) Abstract, 17) Author keywords, 18) Index keywords, 19) Document Type, 20) Publication Stage; 21) Open Access, 22) Source, 23) EID.
23. Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence	Bias mitigation within the research group was ensured through preliminary internal discussions aimed at achieving conceptual, theoretical, and methodological alignment. Each step of the Scoping Review was carried out using blind review procedures among group members. To minimize interpretation bias, a shared glossary of key terms was discussed and agreed upon by all team members.

24. Validation	<p>Two-step validation procedure conducted in two separate phases of the review process. In the first phase, a double-blind screening of a sample of 100 records was conducted independently by four pairs of coders. Inter-coder agreement was assessed using Cohen’s kappa coefficients.</p> <p>In the second phase, final validation and quality control involved a cross-review within each coder pair. Any discrepancies were discussed and resolved through collective deliberation among the reviewers.</p>
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Section 4: Review Results and Discussion

25. Selection of sources of evidence	Sources screened (N): 999
26. Synthesis of results	<p>The findings underscore an urgent need to strengthen research on crisis management, particularly in developing regions, to improve real-time disaster response strategies. Expanding cross-regional collaboration is essential for addressing critical knowledge gaps—especially in Africa, Latin America, and Asia.</p>
27. Limitations	The review can be extended to include additional hazard types and analytical dimensions in the protocol
28. Conclusions	Further attention should be given to underrepresented hazards like droughts and heatwaves, while broadening their scope to include diverse climate risks and balancing long-term adaptation with immediate crisis response.

Adapted from the registration form in:

Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. **PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation.** *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169(7):467–473. doi: 10.7326/M18-0850